

RESIDUAL STRENGTH IN BENDING OF DAMAGED HYBRID SANDWICH PANELS WITH AN ALUMINIUM FOAM CORE

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SUMMARY

Aluminium foam-cored sandwich panels were subjected to indentation and subsequently tested in four-point bending. The bending strength, failure modes and the deformation behavior were studied and compared with those of undamaged panels. It was found that the localised damage does not have a considerable effect on the failure modes and limit loads.

Keywords: Aluminium foam; Sandwich panel; Indentation; Four-point bending; Residual strength

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich panels manufactured with light metallic foam cores are a new class of energy-absorbing materials for specific structural applications, which possess high strength and low weight. For this reason, designing and optimizing lightweight sandwich structures has been of interest to scientists for over a decade. In their applications, they are often subjected to various types of static and dynamic mechanical loadings, some of which lead to localized deformation and even failure. Hence, the response of these panels to local damage, as well as their structural integrity after being locally damaged, is very important.

The bending response of metallic foam core sandwich panels tested under four-point bending configuration has been reported in a number of papers [1-3]. Sha et al. [2] studied the plastic collapse modes of undamaged sandwich panels of Alporas core and aluminium face sheets. Face yielding, core shearing and indentation under the loading roller were observed as the failure modes of the panels, depending on the geometry and the material properties of the panels.

The influence of imperfections (induced by a long cylindrical indenter) on the failure load in four-point bending of sandwich panels comprising of Alporas foam core and aluminium sheets, were also investigated by Bart-smith et al [4]. It was revealed that strong aluminium face sheets invoked the core shear failure mode in the panels, and the imperfection led to a small decrease in the failure load. Conversely, soft skins were

associated with the face yielding failure mode, and the imperfection reduced the failure load more significantly.

MATERIALS AND SAMPLE PREPARATION

Commercial closed-cell aluminium foam (Alporas) with the density of 0.2 g/cm³–0.3 g/cm³, and thicknesses of 6 mm and 12 mm, was employed as the core material. To manufacture the sandwich panels, aluminium sheets of high yield strength alloy (AA 3104-H19) and of low yield strength alloy (AA 1100-O), each with a thickness of 0.32 mm, were utilized as the face sheets. Similar foam core and reinforcing face sheets were already used by the authors in their study of sandwich panels subjected to three-point bending [5].

The cores of the required dimensions were cut off the large foam panels using a band saw, and the aluminium face sheets were cut using a guillotine. All surfaces of the foam core and the skins were degreased and abraded in order to have better adhesion; afterwards they were bonded to each other by a thin epoxy adhesive film (Redux 322) reinforced with a nylon mesh carrier.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The face sheets were tested in tension using an Instron 1185 Universal Mechanical Testing Machine, equipped with a 5kN load-cell and operated at a loading rate of 0.5 mm/min, according to ASTM standard E8-04 [6]. Five dog-bone specimens of each skin were tested.

To investigate the remnant strength of the locally damaged sandwich panels, indentation tests were conducted on the panels to a depth slightly less than their failure indentation depth. Therefore, first indentation tests were carried out until the failure of the panels, and the depth at failure for each panel was recorded.

Hemispherical indenters of diameters 10 mm, 15 mm and 20 mm were utilised for the indentation tests. At least five sandwich panels of each core thickness (6 mm and 12 mm) and of each skin (of high and low yield strength) were failed by each of the indenters. The indentations were carried out using the Instron 1185, under the same conditions as the conducted tensile tests.

Subsequently, an additional set of sandwich panels were prepared and indented to a depth just before failure. As the bending strength was investigated in two occasions, when the damage was located on the compressive side of the beam, and when the damage was located on the tensile side of the beam, twice as many sandwich panels were prepared for the bending tests as for the indentation failure tests. The indented panels were then subjected to quasi-static four-point bending (Figure 1). To eliminate local damage under the loading rollers, rubber tabs of a size 50 mm × 20 mm × 4.5 mm were placed at the contact between the loading rollers and the specimens. The tests were conducted according to standard ASTM C393-00 [7], as the loading span was fixed at $S = 50\text{mm}$, and the distance between the supports was $L = 100\text{mm}$.

Figure 1 Schematic cross-sectional view of four-point bending of the damaged panels: (a) indent on compressive side, (b) indent on tensile side.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The yield strengths of the skins were determined by tensile tests. The estimated yield strength of the employed skin materials are 34 MPa for the low yield strength alloy and 236 MPa for the high yield strength Al alloy.

The indentation tests revealed that the deformation starts with collapsing of the foam beneath the indenter. The panels fail by cracking of the face sheet in the indent, resulting in a sudden drop in the indentation load; the crack is circumferential caused by the radial tensile stress. Figure 2 shows the cross-sectional views of the failed panels for both skin types – it is obvious that the panels laminated with low yield strength aluminium sheets undergo larger deformation at the failure point than the panels laminated with the high yield strength skin.

Figure 2 Cross-sectional view of failed sandwich panels of 12mm foam core by hemispherical indenter of 20 mm diameter: (a) laminated with high yield strength Al alloy (b) laminated with low yield strength Al alloy.

The larger indenters ($2R = 15 \text{ mm}$ and 20 mm) could not fracture the low yield strength skin ($\sigma_y = 34 \text{ MPa}$) in the thin panels of $c = 6 \text{ mm}$, since the densification strain of the foam was reached before the skin failed, and the indentation load increased dramatically with the indentation depth increasing.

The failure indentation depths determined above assisted in the 'safe' indentation of the sandwich panels, so as the panels were indented in their centre to depths slightly lower than the failure depths (Table 1).

Table 1 Indentation depth of the sandwich panels for the residual strength study: “LS” stands for Low Yield Strength and “HS” for High Yield strength.

Indenter diameter (mm)	10				15				20			
	6		12		6		12		6		12	
Core thickness (mm)	LS	HS	LS	HS								
Indentation depth (mm)	3.7	2.2	3.7	2.2	N/A	2.5	4.5	2.5	N/A	2.5	5.7	3

After that, four-point bending of the indented sandwich panels was conducted until failure. Additionally, undamaged panels were also tested to four-point bending, for comparison. The failure modes and failure loads, as well as their dependence on the panels’ geometry, material properties of the foam and the skin, and the volume and location of the contact damage, were of interest. It appears that both undamaged and locally indented sandwich panels fail either by (1) core shear or by (2) core shear and face yielding simultaneously (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Sandwich panels failed by four-point bending by varying skin layer: (a) low yield strength, (b) high yield strength.

The failure modes are affected neither by the location of the damage (tensile or compressive side of the beam), nor by the core thickness. However, both core density and yield strength of the skin have a decisive effect on failure mode of the panels. The observed failure mode is core shear in all cases with the exception of high density foam cores ($\rho > 0.25 \text{ g/cm}^3$) laminated with low yield strength skin ($\sigma_y = 34 \text{ MPa}$); those type of panels failed by core shear and face yielding simultaneously.

The maximum load of the panels in bending tests was determined as the first peak of the load vs. displacement curves. The maximum loads of locally damaged specimens and undamaged panels are shown in Figure 4(a-b). It shows that the indentation damage has minimal effect on limit load of the sandwich panels. This can be explained by the dominant failure mode of the panels, i.e., core shear between inner and outer spans. The failure load of the indented panels is almost independent of whether the indented region is located on the compression or on the tensile side of the panel.

Figure 4 Failure load of the undamaged and indented sandwich panels by varying core thickness, indenter size and damage location: (a) for the panels laminated with high yield strength Al alloy ($\sigma_y=236$ MPa), (b) for the panels laminated with a low yield strength Al alloy ($\sigma_y=34$ MPa).

CONCLUSION

The residual strength of a closed cell aluminium foam core sandwich panels laminated with thin aluminium skins of various yield strengths were investigated in this study. The local damage by hemispherical indenters, slightly before the failure of the skin, does not have a significant influence on load capacity and failure mode of the panels. It was also found that the residual strength, failure mode, and deformation behaviour of the indented panels are not varied whether the indent is on the tensile side of the panel or on compressive side.

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